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In the collection of materials of the conference, the role and role of Science, Education and production in the era of globalization, the pressing problems of the issues of interaction of these processes, feedback on their solutions were presented by mature specialists of the field.

In addition, research on the scientific and practical topic, carried out in the economics, Exact Sciences, Natural Sciences and socio-humanities during the globalization period, information is presented in the scientific and practical fields, which includes the latest innovative technologies in the fields of production.

It can be argued that this collection is one of the specific intersections of current thoughts and innovative ideas of the world of science. This scientific and practical conference was actively attended by professors and scientific researchers engaged in scientific research in Uzbekistan and foreign countries. In increasing the position of the scientific and practical conference, the professors and teachers of domestic and foreign higher educational institutions made a significant contribution.

Professors and teachers of foreign higher educational institutions who actively participated in the work of the conference made a worthy contribution to the high level of interaction with scientists of our country. The processes of international cooperation with foreign countries and exchange with them in the field of Science in the era of globalization have a positive effect on the development of Higher Education, the fields of Science and production. The materials of this conference are special in that they include a wide range of research, from theoretical developments to practical solutions, demonstrating the diversity of approaches and directions in this area.

In conclusion, it should be noted that this scientific and practical conference will be a very useful collection for everyone who is interested in modern research in the fields of further development of Higher Education, Science, Education and production in the era of globalization. The authors are responsible for the content and quality of the articles and abstracts included in the collection.

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O‘ZBEKISTONDA INNOVATSION SIYOSATNING HOLATI VA RIVOJLANISHI

Mukarramova Marjona Komilovna

Mirzo Ulug‘bek nomidagi O‘zbekiston Milliy universiteti Jizzax filiali talabasi

Annotatsiya: Ushbu ishda O‘zbekiston Respublikasida innovatsion siyosatning shakllanishi, amaldagi holati va istiqboldagi rivojlanish yo‘nalishlari tahlil qilinadi. Mamlakatda innovatsion iqtisodiyotni shakllantirish, ilm-fan va texnologiyani iqtisodiyotga integratsiya qilish bo‘yicha amalga oshirilayotgan davlat dasturlari, qonunchilik bazasi hamda institutsional islohotlar ko‘rib chiqiladi. Shuningdek, innovatsion faoliyatni qo‘llab-quvvatlash mexanizmlari, raqamli texnologiyalarni joriy etish va startap ekotizimining rivoji asosiy e‘tibor markazida bo‘ladi. Tadqiqotda mavjud muammolar hamda ularni bartaraf etish bo‘yicha taklif va tavsiyalar beriladi.

Kalit so‘zlar: Innovatsion siyosat, O‘zbekiston, texnologik rivojlanish, innovatsion faoliyat, ilm-fan, startaplar, raqamli texnologiyalar, iqtisodiy modernizatsiya, davlat dasturlari, innovatsion ekotizim.

Bugungi globallashuv va raqamli transformatsiya sharoitida har bir mamlakat taraqqiyoti innovatsion siyosatning to‘g‘ri yo‘lga qo‘yilishiga chambarchas bog‘liq. O‘zbekiston ham bu borada so‘nggi yillarda tub islohotlarni amalga oshirmoqda. Innovatsion yondashuvlar, ilm-fan yutuqlari va texnologik yangiliklar iqtisodiyotning barcha sohalariga kirib bormoqda.

Avvalo, O‘zbekiston Respublikasining Prezidentining tashabbusi bilan 2018-yilda Innovatsion rivojlanish vazirligi tashkil etildi [1]. Ushbu vazirlik innovatsion faoliyatni muvofiqlashtirish, ilg‘or g‘oyalarni qo‘llab-quvvatlash va ilmiy tadqiqotlarni tijoratlashtirish borasida muhim rol o‘ynamoqda. Davlat tomonidan innovatsion loyihalarga subsidiya, grant va boshqa moliyaviy yordamlar ajratilishi, tadbirkorlar va yosh olimlar uchun yaratilayotgan imkoniyatlar mamlakat innovatsion salohiyatining yuksalishiga xizmat qilmoqda.

Shu bilan birga, O‘zbekistonda raqamli iqtisodiyotga o‘tish, “Elektron hukumat”, “Raqamli O‘zbekiston – 2030” strategiyalari doirasida axborot-kommunikatsiya texnologiyalarini keng joriy etish innovatsion siyosatning asosiy yo‘nalishlaridan biri bo‘lib qolmoqda [2]. Hududlarda innovatsion markazlar, texnoparklar va startap zonalari tashkil etilayotgani zamonaviy texnologiyalarni ishlab chiqish va amaliyotga joriy qilishga zamin yaratmoqda.

Biroq mavjud yutuqlarga qaramay, ayrim muammolar ham saqlanib qolmoqda. Jumladan, ilmiy-tadqiqot ishlari va ishlab chiqarish o‘rtasidagi uzviy bog‘liqlik yetarli emas, yosh olimlarni innovatsion faoliyatga keng jalb qilishda tizimli yondashuv talab etiladi. Innovatsiyalarni tijoratlashtirish va intellektual

mulkni himoya qilish mexanizmlarining to'liq ishlamasligi ham dolzarb muammolardan sanaladi.

O'zbekistonda innovatsion siyosat yangi bosqichga ko'tarilmoqda. Davlatning bu yo'nalishga bo'lgan e'tibori, qonunchilikdagi o'zgarishlar va xalqaro hamkorlik dasturlari ushbu siyosatning barqaror rivojlanishiga xizmat qiladi. Kelgusida innovatsion yondashuvni ta'lim, sog'liqni saqlash, sanoat va boshqa sohalarda keng joriy etish orqali raqobatbardosh, bilimga asoslangan iqtisodiyotni shakllantirish mumkin bo'ladi.

XULOSA

O'zbekiston Respublikasida innovatsion siyosatning shakllanishi va rivojlanishi so'nggi yillarda yangi bosqichga ko'tarildi. Mamlakatda innovatsiyalarni qo'llab-quvvatlash, ilm-fanni amaliyot bilan bog'lash va raqamli texnologiyalarni keng joriy etish bo'yicha tizimli islohotlar amalga oshirilmoqda. Davlat siyosatining ustuvor yo'nalishlaridan biri sifatida innovatsion taraqqiyot uchun zarur shart-sharoitlar yaratilmoqda. Biroq, mavjud muammolar — kadrlar salohiyati, ilmiy tadqiqotlarning tijoratlashtirilishi va texnologik uzilishlar — samarali hal etilishi lozim bo'lgan dolzarb vazifalardir. Innovatsion siyosatning izchil va maqsadli yuritilishi mamlakat iqtisodiyotining barqaror o'sishi hamda xalqaro raqobatbardoshligini ta'minlashda muhim omil bo'lib xizmat qiladi.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar ro'yxati:

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